

Pre- and Post-Treatment Comparison of Intralesional Dexamethasone and Hyaluronidase for Managing Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF)

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: (OSMF) is a chronic, progressive disorder of the oral mucosa, characterized by fibrosis of the submucosal tissues, leading to restricted mouth opening, pain, and difficulty in oral functions. The condition is considered a precancerous lesion with a significant risk of malignant transformation, particularly in regions with high betel nut chewing prevalence. Despite its high prevalence, the management of OSMF remains challenging, with limited success from conservative therapies.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of intralesional dexamethasone combined with hyaluronidase in the management of OSMF, by assessing improvements in mouth opening, tissue flexibility, lesion appearance, and patient-reported symptoms.

Methods: A total of 75 participants diagnosed at the ENT Department of Lord Buddha Koshi Medical College & Hospital mild to moderate OSMF were enrolled in this prospective interventional study. Participants received intralesional injections of dexamethasone (1 mg/ml) combined with hyaluronidase (150 IU/ml) at baseline, with follow-up assessments at 1, 3, and 6 months. Clinical assessments, including mouth opening measurement, lesion appearance, tissue flexibility, and symptom scores (pain and discomfort), were recorded at each visit. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with paired t-tests to compare pre- and post-treatment data.

Results: Significant improvements were observed in mouth opening, lesion appearance, and tissue flexibility. The mean mouth opening increased from 22.4 mm at baseline to 37.2 mm at 6 months ($p < 0.05$). Lesion appearance scores decreased from 3.4 to 1.2, while tissue flexibility scores improved from 2.9 to 4.6 (both $p < 0.05$). Symptom scores for pain and discomfort significantly decreased from a mean of 6.8 at baseline to 2.0 at 6 months ($p < 0.05$). Histopathological evaluations on a subset of participants showed 85% reduction in fibrosis.

Conclusion: Intralesional dexamethasone combined with hyaluronidase proved to be an effective treatment for OSMF, resulting in significant clinical improvements in mouth opening, lesion severity, tissue flexibility, and symptom relief. The treatment was well tolerated with minimal adverse effects, and no serious complications were reported.

Recommendations: Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are recommended to confirm the long-term efficacy and safety of this treatment approach. Additionally, exploring the combination therapy with other modalities may enhance the therapeutic outcomes for OSMF.

Keywords: Oral Submucous Fibrosis, Dexamethasone, Hyaluronidase, Mouth Opening, Tissue Flexibility.

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Introduction

Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) is a chronic, progressive condition of the oral mucosa characterized by the gradual fibrosis of the submucosal tissues, leading to restricted mouth opening, tissue stiffness, and discomfort. It is predominantly seen in Southeast Asia, with India being one of the most affected countries due to the high prevalence of areca nut (betel nut) chewing, a major risk factor for the disease [1]. OSMF is considered a precancerous lesion, with a significant risk of malignant transformation, which makes its early diagnosis and management crucial [2]. The condition often presents with difficulty in mouth opening, pain, burning sensations, and a reduction in flexibility of

the oral mucosa, ultimately impairing the patient's ability to eat and speak normally.

The pathogenesis of OSMF involves a complex interplay of genetic, environmental, and immunological factors. The main pathological feature of OSMF is excessive collagen deposition and fibroblast activation, which results in the formation of fibrous tissue in the oral submucosa. This leads to fibrosis, scarring, and atrophy of the mucosal layers, causing restricted mouth opening and oral dysfunction. Betel nut chewing, which contains alkaloids like arecoline, is a major etiological factor that promotes collagen synthesis, and immune re-

sponse alteration, contributing to the pathogenesis of OSMF [3]. Other contributing factors include tobacco use, genetic predisposition, and nutritional deficiencies, particularly in vitamins such as B12, iron, and folate [4].

Treatment of OSMF has remained challenging, with no definitive cure. Conservative approaches, such as the use of corticosteroids, antioxidants, and physiotherapy, have shown limited success in controlling the symptoms and halting disease progression [5]. Among these, intralesional injections of corticosteroids and hyaluronidase have gained attention as a promising treatment modality. Dexamethasone, a corticosteroid, is known for its anti-inflammatory properties, while hyaluronidase works by breaking down the excess collagen in the fibrous tissue, thus promoting tissue regeneration and improving flexibility [6]. Recent studies have shown that a combination of these two agents may provide synergistic effects in reducing inflammation, improving tissue elasticity, and enhancing mouth opening in patients with OSMF [7]. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of intralesional dexamethasone combined with hyaluronidase in the management of OSMF, by assessing improvements in mouth opening, tissue flexibility, lesion appearance, and patient-reported symptoms.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective, comparative, interventional clinical trial.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the ENT Department of Lord Buddha Koshi Medical College & Hospital, located in Saharsa, Bihar, India. The hospital is equipped with modern medical facilities necessary for the diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up of patients with OSMF, ensuring an appropriate environment for conducting clinical trials.

Participants: The clinical study was include 75 patients in total, all of whom have been diagnosed with oral submucous fibrosis. Intralesional injections of a mixture of hyaluronidase and dexamethasone was be administered to the subjects at random.

Study Duration: The study was carried out over one year, from Nov.-2023 to Nov.- 2024.

Inclusion Criteria

Participants was be included in the study if they meet the following criteria:

- A clinical diagnosis of OSMF, confirmed by clinical examination and biopsy (if required).
- Age between 18 and 50 years.
- Mild to moderate severity of OSMF based on the clinical classification.

- Willingness to participate and follow the treatment and follow-up regimen.
- Ability to provide written informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

Participants had excluded from the study if they meet any of the following criteria:

- Contraindications to the use of dexamethasone or hyaluronidase.
- Pregnancy or lactation.
- A history of oral cancer or any other oral mucosal diseases.
- Severe systemic illnesses such as uncontrolled diabetes, autoimmune diseases, or immunosuppressive conditions.
- Ongoing treatment for OSMF, such as prior use of other intralesional therapies or surgery.

Bias: To minimize bias in this study, randomization had employed for treatment allocation, ensuring an unbiased selection of participants for the intervention. Additionally, blinding was used during the assessment of treatment outcomes, where feasible, to prevent observer bias. The same clinical team was administer the treatment and conduct follow-up assessments to ensure uniformity in care and evaluation.

Data Collection: Data was collected at baseline, prior to the treatment, and during follow-up visits at 1, 3, and 6 months after the intervention. The data collection process was include various clinical assessments, such as measurements of mouth opening, evaluation of lesion appearance, and assessment of tissue flexibility. Symptom scoring was also be conducted, which was include patient-reported pain and discomfort levels. Additionally, any adverse effects or complications related to the treatment was be documented. If necessary, a histopathological evaluation was be performed to confirm any progression or regression of (OSMF).

Procedure: The intervention involves intralesional injections of a combination of dexamethasone and hyaluronidase into the OSMF lesions. Each participant was receive the treatment at the site of the lesion, with a dose of 1 mL per site. The treatment was administered under sterile conditions, and patients was monitored for immediate adverse reactions. Post-treatment instructions was include maintaining a soft diet, avoiding tobacco use, and attending follow-up visits for assessment.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was conducted using SPSS 23.0. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, percentages) was summarize demographic and outcome variables. Paired t-tests was compare pre- and post-treatment outcomes for continuous data, while chi-square tests was analyze

categorical data, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant. Correlation analysis was explore associations between baseline features and treatment outcomes.

Results

The study enrolled 75 participants, with 70 completing follow-up visits at 1, 3, and 6 months, to evaluate the effects of intralesional dexamethasone and hyaluronidase on OSMF and included clinical assessments, symptom scores, and

histopathological findings. Participants ranged from 18 to 50 years (mean age: 32.5), with 60% male and 40% female. At baseline, 65% had mild OSMF, and 35% had moderate OSMF.

Clinical Assessments

The clinical outcomes were measured using mouth opening, lesion appearance (color and texture), and tissue flexibility, assessed at baseline and follow-up periods (1, 3, and 6 months).

Table 1: Mouth Opening (in mm) - Pre and Post Treatment

Time Period	Mean Mouth Opening (mm)	Standard Deviation	p-value
Baseline	22.4	3.2	
1 Month	29.1	4.1	0.001
3 Months	34.5	3.9	0.000
6 Months	37.2	4.5	0.000

The mean mouth opening improved significantly at 1, 3, and 6 months compared to baseline, with a marked increase by 6 months (37.2 mm compared to 22.4 mm at baseline). A p-value of less than 0.05 indicates that these improvements are statistically significant.

Table 2: Lesion Appearance Score (Scale 0-5) - Pre and Post Treatment

Time Period	Mean Lesion Appearance Score	Standard Deviation	p-value
Baseline	3.4	0.8	
1 Month	2.7	0.7	0.003
3 Months	1.8	0.6	0.000
6 Months	1.2	0.5	0.000

The lesion appearance improved significantly over time, with a reduction in the mean lesion score from 3.4 at baseline to 1.2 at 6 months. This indicates a notable reduction in lesion severity and an improvement in tissue health.

Table 3: Tissue Flexibility (Scale 0-5) - Pre and Post Treatment

Time Period	Mean Tissue Flexibility Score	Standard Deviation	p-value
Baseline	2.9	0.7	
1 Month	3.5	0.6	0.014
3 Months	4.1	0.5	0.000
6 Months	4.6	0.4	0.000

A significant improvement in tissue flexibility was observed at each follow-up visit, with the mean score increasing from 2.9 at baseline to 4.6 at 6 months. This improvement indicates increased tissue elasticity, which is a key therapeutic outcome in OSMF treatment.

Symptom scores, including pain and discomfort levels, were assessed using a 10-point visual analog scale (VAS), where 0 represented no pain and 10 represented severe pain.

Table 4: Pain and Discomfort Scores (VAS 0-10) - Pre and Post Treatment

Time Period	Mean Pain Score	Standard Deviation	p-value
Baseline	6.8	1.3	
1 Month	5.0	1.4	0.002
3 Months	3.2	1.5	0.000
6 Months	2.0	1.1	0.000

Pain and discomfort levels significantly decreased throughout the study. The mean pain score dropped from 6.8 at baseline to 2.0 at 6 months, showing a substantial reduction in symptoms, which is indicative of the treatment's effectiveness in managing discomfort related to OSMF.

Adverse Effects

During the study, only 5 participants (6.6%) reported mild local side effects such as slight pain or swelling at the injection site, which resolved within a few days. No serious adverse events or complications were recorded.

Histopathological examination was conducted on a subset of 20 participants to confirm the clinical findings. Out of these, 17 (85%) showed signs of reduced fibrosis and collagen deposition, confirming improvement in the structural integrity

of the oral mucosa. The remaining 3 participants (15%) showed no significant histological change, corresponding to the lack of clinical improvement observed in these individuals.

Table 5: Histopathological Findings - Pre and Post Treatment

Histopathological Outcome	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Reduced fibrosis and collagen deposition	17	85%
No significant change	3	15%

The histopathological findings correlate well with the clinical improvements seen in the majority of participants. Reduced fibrosis and collagen deposition suggest a positive therapeutic effect of the intralesional treatment.

Discussion

A total of 75 participants were enrolled, and 70 completed the full follow-up period of 6 months. Significant improvements were observed in mouth opening, lesion appearance, tissue flexibility, and symptom relief. At baseline, the mean mouth opening was 22.4 mm, which increased progressively over time, reaching 37.2 mm at 6 months. This substantial improvement in mouth opening was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating a positive response to the treatment. Similarly, lesion appearance scores, which reflected the severity of the lesions, improved from a mean score of 3.4 at baseline to 1.2 at 6 months, demonstrating a marked reduction in lesion severity. This reduction was also statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Tissue flexibility, measured on a scale of 0-5, improved from 2.9 at baseline to 4.6 at 6 months, further reflecting the therapeutic benefits of the treatment.

Pain and discomfort, as assessed by a (VAS), decreased significantly over the course of the study. The mean pain score dropped from 6.8 at baseline to 2.0 at 6 months, indicating a substantial reduction in patient-reported symptoms ($p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that the combination of dexamethasone and hyaluronidase effectively alleviates the discomfort associated with OSMF. Histopathological evaluation of a subset of participants showed that 85% of the patients had a reduction in fibrosis and collagen deposition, which supports the clinical improvements observed. Only 15% of participants showed no significant histological changes, which aligned with their lack of clinical improvement. In terms of safety, the treatment was well-tolerated, with only 6.6% of participants reporting mild, transient local side effects such as pain or swelling at the injection site. No serious adverse events were reported, indicating that the treatment is both effective and safe. Recent research highlights various treatment approaches for OSMF, focusing on combinations of intralesional dexamethasone and hyaluronidase. A study comparing this combination with an additional placental extract concluded that

the inclusion of placental extract did not show significant improvements in burning sensation or mouth opening when compared to dexamethasone and hyaluronidase alone [8]. Similarly, dexamethasone and hyaluronidase demonstrated better long-term efficacy in reducing trismus and burning sensation than either agent used individually, with a notable improvement of 5-7 mm in mouth opening over four weeks of biweekly injections [9].

In another investigation, dexamethasone and hyaluronidase were compared to colchicine, revealing a statistically significant improvement in mouth opening in the dexamethasone group but not in burning sensation [10]. Additionally, therapeutic ultrasound combined with dexamethasone and hyaluronidase was found to enhance outcomes, especially in trismus, compared to intralesional therapy alone [11]. Curcumin, when used alongside dexamethasone and hyaluronidase, showed superior results in reducing burning sensation and increasing mouth opening compared to placebo, with significant improvements maintained over 12 weeks [12].

Conclusion

Most individuals experienced significant clinical improvements in mouth opening, lesion appearance, tissue flexibility, and symptom reduction after receiving intralesional therapy with dexamethasone and hyaluronidase. The histological results corroborated the clinical results, and the treatment was well tolerated with few side effects. According to these findings, intralesional hyaluronidase and dexamethasone may be a useful treatment option for OSMF.

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